

Museum Theory

Ryan J. Buchanan

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Abstract

We propose a novel cognitive framework in which cognitive agents interact with their environment by assigning meta-tags which serve to collect related objects via stereotypes. Associated to each cognitive object is a museum, whose properties are enshrined by exhibits which may be visited by agents. Cognitive agents (consciously or unconsciously) curate museums in order to perfect them as self-representative stereotypes.

1 Introduction

Let us begin with some notation.

Notation 1.1. *If p has the properties of P , we write $p : P$ and say “ p has type P ”.*

Definition 1.1 (Elementality). $(p : P) \ \& \ (P \supset p) \longrightarrow p \in P$

Axiom 1.1. *If $p \in P$, then $\forall p_i \in p$, we have $p_i : P$*

Definition 1.2 (Monomorphism). $c : C \ \& \ c \rightarrow C$

Definition 1.3 (Epimorphism). $c : C \ \& \ C \rightarrow c$

Here, \rightarrow is the standard logical implication; write $C \twoheadrightarrow c$ for an epimorphism and $c \hookrightarrow C$ for a monomorphism.

Notation 1.2. *Let $type(p) = P \ \forall p : P$*

Proposition 1.1. $\forall p \ \exists type(p) \ s.t. \ p : type(p)$

Proposition 1.2 (Downwards closure). *Let \mathfrak{p} be a flag. Then*

$$type(inf(\mathfrak{p})) : type(sup(\mathfrak{p}))$$

Proof. The type of a sub-object is a subtype of the object’s type. □

Example 1.1. *Let A and B be open neighborhood, with $A \subset B$. Then, $type(B)$ contains $type(A)$ as a full subtype.*

Remark 1.1. *This says that local types are more special than global ones.*

Lemma 1.1. $(A|_\phi) \& (\mathbf{type}(A) : \mathbf{type}(B)) \longrightarrow B|_\phi$

Proof. $(\mathbf{type}(A) : \mathbf{type}(B)) \longrightarrow A : B \longrightarrow \forall a \in A \exists \iota : a \hookrightarrow B$ □

Definition 1.4. *If*

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} a_i = \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} b_i$$

then we say a asymptotically approximates b , and write

$$a \propto b$$

Definition 1.5. *If, for some j ,*

$$a_{\geq j} = b_{\geq j}$$

we say a approximates b .

Notation 1.3. *If a approximates b , write $a \underline{\propto} b$*

Remark 1.2. *We may call the second approximation strong approximation to distinguish it from asymptotic approximation.*

Definition 1.6 (Stereotype). *Let $a : S$ and $b : S$. If $a \propto S$ and $b \propto S$, then S is a stereotype if and only if a approximates b .*

Formally, let $B = [a, b]$

$$S \text{ is a stereotype} = B : S \& B \propto S \& a : S \underline{\propto} b : S$$

Definition 1.7 (Exhibit). *Let $\lambda_0 = [\lambda, \Lambda]$ and $\lambda : \Lambda$. Let $S_0 = [\lambda_0, S]$ and let S be a stereotype of λ_0 . An exhibit is the smallest j such that*

$$(\forall a \forall b) : \lambda_0$$

$$a_j = b_j$$

Thus, if $a_j : S$, then $b_j : S$ means that a and b share an exhibit. To put it in adjectival terms, a and b exhibit the same property, j , such that

$$[\text{Property } 1] \ a_j : j \& b_j : j \& j : S$$

Proposition 1.3.

$$\forall \phi := \{a_j, b_j | \text{Property } 1 \text{ is satisfied}\} \exists S \text{ s.t. } \phi \in S$$

Definition 1.8 (Meta-tag). $\{\mu \mid \mu : \phi \hookrightarrow S\}$

Cognitive agents freely assign meta-tags to perceptive stimuli. For each interaction between an agent \mathfrak{A} and a stimulus \mathfrak{s} , we have

Definition 1.9 (Visits). $v = (\mathfrak{A} \& \mathfrak{s}) \& d(\mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{s}) < 2\varepsilon \longrightarrow \mu := \phi : \mathfrak{s} \wedge \mathfrak{A} \longrightarrow \phi \hookrightarrow S$

Essentially, a visit is a mechanism by which agents label their environment. Roughly speaking,

$$\text{measurements on } \mathfrak{s} = \mathfrak{A}v\mathfrak{s} \rightarrow \{a_i, b_i\} : \mathfrak{s} : S$$

where $\mathfrak{A}v\mathfrak{s}$ is to be read “ \mathfrak{A} visits \mathfrak{s} .” To avoid clutter, from now on write

$$\mathfrak{A} \overset{v}{\leftrightarrow} \mathfrak{s}$$

Theorem 1.1. $\mathfrak{A} \overset{v}{\leftrightarrow} \mathfrak{s} \iff \exists \mathfrak{A} \& \exists \mathfrak{s}$

Definition 1.10 (Relata). For $\phi \in A$ and $\phi' \in B$, if we obtain two meta-tags, $\mu : \phi \hookrightarrow S$ and $\mu' : \phi' \hookrightarrow S'$ such that $S = S'$, then $t(\mu) = t(\mu')$ and we say that A and B are related. Every element in the class $[B] = \neg(A) / \sim$ is called a “relatum,” the plural of which is “relata.”

Remark 1.3.

2 Cognitive prisms

It is at this juncture that our theory takes on a geometric flavor. We will introduce now the idea of a “cognitive prism,” which is an extremely simple cognitive framework I postulate agents use as a prototype when observing their environments.

Let $\nu(X)$ be the outer measure of X . Let $X = \{\#v, \#\lambda_0, \#\text{relata}\}$. Then, we can form a three-dimensional prism called a “cognitive prism” consisting of these dimensions. There exists, for every agent, and every concept with which the agent may engage, a unique bijection $\mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{A}) \leftrightarrow \nu(\mathcal{M})$; the agent is unable to distinguish between the two, and so their equivocation is always a “behind the scenes” process. The following is our main theorem:

Theorem 2.1. *The identity of a museum \mathcal{M} is asymptotically approximated by $\nu(\mathcal{M})$.*

This makes sense if we see individuation as a function of time, as we can view entropy as a growth of $\nu(\mathcal{M})$. When this growth is proportional, then the process is ergodic. Thus:

Theorem 2.2. *Ergodic cognitive prisms approximate perfect stereotypes.*

A perfect stereotype, \mathcal{S} is one that perfectly describes all of its constituents using the fewest number of meta-tags. I.e., given perfect knowledge of \mathcal{S} , one obtains perfect knowledge of all $s : \mathcal{S}$ for which \mathcal{S} is a stereotype. Therefore, we can make the following definition

Definition 2.1. *A perfect stereotype of a museum is the stereotype for which the coinciding cognitive prism is a perfect replica.*

Thus, if

$$\mu : \nu(\mathcal{M}) \hookrightarrow \mathcal{S}$$

is trivial, then μ perfectly locates every aspect of \mathcal{M} in the corresponding state space. That is to say, as the identity of an object individuates with respect to observation, it becomes maximally self-similar to its platonic ideal. This is to say, in informal terms “the map asymptotically approximates the territory.”

Proposition 2.1. *Cognitive prisms with a disproportionate ratio of visits to exhibits to relata are more likely to be treated as meta-tags, whereas more-or-less ergodic ones are more likely to be treated as stereotypes.*

The reasoning behind this proposition is that, as the mental representation of a museum becomes distorted over time, it will either have a highly visited exhibit, or an oligarchy consisting of highly visited exhibits, or there will be too many relata (i.e., too much noise) in order for it to be used as a precise stereotype. Thus, the mind favors symmetry; or at least, the most symmetric cognitive prisms are likely to be interpreted as the “realest,” in the sense of depth, without respect to their actuality.¹

Assumption 2.1 (Multiplicity). $\mathcal{M} \supset \mu \quad \forall \mu \rightarrow S \neq \mathcal{S}$

This essentially says that every subject/object has more than just a single property, with the caveat being that the property is not perfectly stereotypical; that is to say, objects are always multi-dimensional, in the sense that they are tokens of more than one dimension. Bear in mind, these dimensions are more-or-less subjective, but sometimes, the subjective does coincide with the empirical; the prototypical example are the three basis vectors of \mathbb{R}^3 , which seem to do a remarkable job of modelling the physical world around us.

Notice that, if spacetime is discrete, then an object’s relative positioning within it (with respect to any reference frame) contains only finite information; otherwise, an infinite amount of information is contained by knowing the coordinates of an object, and therefore an infinite amount of energy would be required to compute it. Thus, it is conjectured by O. Hancock that a smooth universe with smooth group actions if and only if the universe is non-computational.

2.1 Cognitive lightcones

This framework is somewhat similar to Michael Levin’s “cognitive lightcone” project.² Levin defines an agent as a being, \mathcal{B} whose evolution coincides with some “goal state.” This is useful for practical purposes, for instance, as he points out, to distinguish between cancer and the being which is colonized by the tumor.

As the complexity of \mathcal{B} is increased, its goals become less bound to its immediate frame of reference; A. Korzybski called this ability “time-binding,” and used it to distinguish from “lower animals,” which relied on “space-binding.”

¹In specific, the “realest” museums may be the most difficult to actualize.

²see [1]

Thus, there is some set $b \in \text{int}(\mathcal{B})$ which both lies in the interior of \mathcal{B} (which we are assuming, for ease of argumentation, to be topological), and reflects the *intention* of the being itself.

If the being is successful in achieving its goal, then $b \underline{\propto} \mathcal{B}$ as after a definite amount of time. However, the goals of \mathcal{B} influence the formation of the perfect stereotype $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{B})$, despite the fact that the stereotype itself lacks agency. Philosophically, this is somewhat of a conundrum. Either we must attribute agency to \mathcal{S} , or we must admit that the creation³ of the stereotype is the ultimate productive goal of the organism.

Proposition 2.2. $b \underline{\propto} \mathcal{B} \longrightarrow \mathcal{B} \propto \text{amb}(\mathcal{B})$

“Mankind is an abstraction.” - F. Nietzsche, *The Will to Power*

Here, $\text{amb}(\mathcal{B})$ can be thought of as a social holon (in the sense of F. Kofman⁴); i.e., a clique, “crowd,” or society. Notice that a society may be spread out dramatically in space, but is culturally bound through time. Now, this principle says that as an agent individuates towards the actualization of its goal state, then the individual will asymptotically approximate the society in which it is a part of. Notice that while the approximation of an individual by its goal state is strong, the approximation of society at large by the individual is merely asymptotic.

Proposition 2.3. $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int d\mathcal{B}_t = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} d\nu(\text{amb}(\mathcal{B}))_t$

As we progress in time, morphology of the cognitive prism associated with an individual’s society will eventually become ergodic. This equation, of course, assumes that the agent outlives all others, and so it is technically incomplete. In order to correct it, we must add a noise term to the left-hand-side so that it resembles Langevin’s equation:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\int d\mathcal{B}_t \right) + \delta_{t_i} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} d\nu(\text{amb}(\mathcal{B}))_t \quad i \in I$$

Now, at every moment t , we have a collection of possible update states drawn from an index set I . These represent stochastic, time-dependent mutations to our agent which modify the stereotypes that are formed about the group to which it belongs.⁵

Proposition 2.4. $P(\text{amb}(\mathcal{B})|\mathcal{B}) > P(\text{amb}(\mathcal{B})|\delta_{t_i})$

This tells us that, given a society consisting of agents with stochastic mutations, we are more likely to obtain the society by beginning with the agents and applying random mutations, then we are if we begin with a random agent and apply the correct mutations. Abstracting a bit,

$$P(\nu(X)|X) > P(\nu(X)|\nu(\bullet))$$

³Better yet, *Daseinization*

⁴see [4]

⁵Here, I mean group in the plain English sense, with no mathematical baggage.

As we can see, the museum itself is doing more work for us than the cognitive prism. This is a sort of Kantian perspective, suggesting that the “thing-in-itself” is really out there somewhere, and to a greater degree influences the nature of our observation than our own mechanisms for perceiving it. Granted, both the perspective itself, as well as the object of perception, are both factors in the ultimate perception of a being, but their weight is not equal. We have

$$\text{Thing} = \frac{m(X) + n(\nu(X))}{2} \quad m > n$$

which reflects this.

A References

- [1] M. Levin, *The Computational Boundary of a “Self”: Developmental Bioelectricity Drives Multicellularity and Scale-Free Cognition*, (2019)
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- [4] F. Kofman, *Holons, Heaps, and Artifacts*, (2014)
- [5] I. Kant, *Prolegomena to any Future Metaphysics*, (1783)